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Energy Efficient Measures In The Development Of The Built Environment In Nigeria: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Energy efficiency in buildings has attracted attention amongst construction stakeholders towards enhancing users' comfort. It involves the effective management of energy in powering buildings which translates into reductions in emissions of harmful greenhouse gases, thereby making the environment safer and preserving future generations. This study reviews the energy efficiency measures in buildings in Nigeria, and provides insights on prospects and challenges for improvements, towards enhancing sustainable development and reductions in building energy consumption patterns in the country. The qualitative research involves a desktop review of peer reviewed articles downloaded from six data bases to include Google Scholar, Semantics, Researchgate, Proquest, Science Direct and Scopus. After a thorough search, N=84 papers were selected for review from which inferences were drawn. Data drawn from the reviews were content analyzed and presented descriptively with texts which revealed that modern adoption of sustainable building materials, innovations in energy efficiency studies and implementation of sustainability in building materials used within the built environment is evidently lacking in Nigeria. It concludes by revealing the sundry benefits of energy efficient measures especially in achieving sustainable communities' development, improving habitable spaces and improving livable urban environments. Inferences derived from the review would be beneficial to construction stakeholders, government policy makers, academia, building materials suppliers and the business communities towards enhancing the development of the built environment further in Nigeria.

Keywords: Assessment, Government, Energy Efficiency, Roles, Technologies, Implications, Environment.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Sub Saharan Africa has in the past decade witnessed a rapid population growth which has exacerbated the dependence of buildings on fossil based fuels as a means of energy generation and consumption. This has resulted in the alarming consequences which buildings have created in the built environment thereby causing global warming with environmental degradations (Zoure and Genevese 2023). It is therefore worthy to note that the use of traditional biomass fuels does not only result in environmental pollution but also results in household air pollutions Murshed (2022). These pollutions are associated with respiratory illnesses including cardiovascular diseases and also enhances the prevalence of overweight diseases

amongst children under the ages of five. Buildings consume a lot of energy during operations with their associated equipment's and it is generally acknowledged that steps should be taken at reducing these huge building power usages during their useful life. It is to this end that this study was conducted to examine efforts being made at improving the building energy consumption levels during the erection and functioning within building structures for the Nigerian market, while also providing insight on prospects, challenges and possible solutions in developing sustainable buildings with livable surrounding environments. As a means of reducing energy consumption patterns, (Loengbudnark, Kharlipour, Bharathy, Voinov and Thomas 2023) suggested that this can be achieved by allowing building occupants interact with the building systems within them. Other scholars, (Sharifishourabi, Dincer and Mohany 2023) in suggesting ways of alleviating the emissions of harmful greenhouse gases which pollute areas around most buildings and their built environments due to fossil based sources, these have encouraged suggestions of allowing alternative sources of energy generation to be applied with cleaner and more reliable deliverable. Due to huge consumption patterns of using fossil based fuels in energy generation for most buildings and infrastructural facilities, there is a huge attention and anxiety amongst construction stakeholders towards enhancing user comfort (Mousavi, Gheibi, Waclawek and Behzadian 2023).

In their study on effectively managing the consumption patterns of energy generation in academic buildings, (Ashrafian 2023) believes that incorporating future weather predictions as an assessment of a buildings effectiveness in withstanding the effects of adverse weather conditions and improving comfort within is an innovative way in responding to climate change. Energy efficiency in buildings is also achieved by increased levels of energy usage amongst new builds and old builds as their needs arises. While further proffering solutions at achieving energy efficiency in buildings, (Kiviste, Musakka, Ruus and Vinha 2023) noted that this can play a landmark role for further reductions in global warming by the building stock. Past urban center's that have experienced urbanization processes have continued to possess the possibility of accumulating huge stocks of non-energy efficient buildings and by direct consequence, having continuous huge energy dependence patterns (Chen, Cao, Yuan, Huo and Cai 2023). It has been established that since the turn of the millennium, consumption patterns and energy management within houses and offices have been an interesting topic of discussion amongst researchers all over the world, (Danish, Senjyu, Ibrahim, Ahmadi and Howlader 2019).

Further studies by (D'Adamo, Mammetti, Ottaviani and Ozturk 2023) have highlighted the importance in developing further, the research carried out by a group of households whereby communities are now being seen as a place where energy independence and sustainability are achievable and placing dependence on renewables and photovoltaics. While also suggesting innovative ways of achieving energy efficiency in buildings and improving further comfort levels of building occupants, (Salazar, Vargas-Lopez, Yang, Li and Hernandez-Lopez 2023) have proposed considering the savings in energy and CO₂ reductions emission's which they believe will be achieved by multi-glazing strategies when considering design parameters of buildings due to additions of more glass layers. Other ways to increase energy efficiency in buildings, suggested by (Chien, Huang and Zhao 2023) include, adopting more energy efficient technologies, implementation of better production process that are available, further reductions in energy loses and use of energy efficiency resources that are renewable, replenishable and recyclable. On the other hand, decreasing greenhouse gas emissions in buildings which is one of the major concerns of stakeholders towards mitigating global warming can be achieved at all phases in the projects development from take-off to the buildings operational stage and the buildings end of life stage (Calender and Thollander 2023).

The primary concern of governments and countries over the world is the dangers posed by large building stocks and their huge energy consumption patterns that release greenhouse gases into the built environment which have become a source of threat to the environment and the globe at large. To this end, governments and policy makers in trying to meet their commitments at improving energy efficient developments and environmental transitions by 2030 are focusing attention at establishing benchmarks of environmental sustainability and clean energy generation. In Nigeria, guidelines have been proposed within the energy sector policy guidelines in using alternative sources of energy such as renewables and solar energy design strategies in the design and construction of buildings which have arisen out of

copying existing building codes. These suggested measures to be adopted include developing building codes with energy studies being a major focus and understanding design strategies that focus on reductions in buildings energy generation and consumption patterns and further improving the buildings relationship with its immediate built environment in Nigeria.

Therefore, this study is beneficial for providing insight on the efforts being made towards reducing dependence on fossil based fuels being used up by buildings in the Nigerian built environment. It highlights the prospects and challenges being faced in the industry towards developing energy efficient buildings and environments. The study also aligns and helps in promoting two out of the several (SDG) goals. These are goal seven which involves making sure that access to modern energy for everyone is realizable, affordable and sustainable; and the eleventh goal that encourages the development of inclusive and safer communities that are resilient and sustainable.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

The review was conducted using PRISMA 2020 flow diagram (Page, McKenzie, Bossuyt, Boutron, Hoffmann, Mulrow and Moher 2021). The processes carried out for eligibility, inclusion and exclusion of articles were carefully connected and finally synthesized to arrive at articles that shed light on the studies area of focus and represented in Fig 1.

Figure 1: Identification, Search and Screening Process of Consulted Articles

2.1 Identification, Search and Screening Process

The research is a combination of an in-depth review of ground breaking works on energy efficiency, innovative building construction materials and processes; these were available in documented literatures on various aspects of sustainability, thereby enhancing energy efficiency in buildings in Nigeria with supporting literature for comparisons internationally. The study focused on the repository of literature research from six science related publishers- Google Scholar, Semantics, Researchgate, Proquest, Science Direct and Scopus from the period spanning 2015 to 2023. Since the study was a literature review, the research design was a qualitative research methodology that consulted literature from these repositories extensively. This research design was chosen because qualitative research methods are exploratory and provide deeper insight into the studies area of focus, thereby further exploring issues related to the study. The data sources for the study were relevant literature that shed more light on the areas of focus of the study. A comprehensive search strategy was developed for the study whereby relevant keywords were

searched in the six databases to arrive at relevant literature to guide the studies area of focus. Papers reviewed were N=84. In excluding some and including some in the research documents, the main factor for inclusion of some of the literature was as a result of selecting articles that had an appropriate study design for the documentation of the literature review. Results were presented using a thematic analysis whereby themes were presented cohesively. These were further subdivided into conference proceedings, review papers and articles. In the study, data was interpreted by applying a four step process of firstly assembling all the information needed for the study, secondly, developing findings from the literature gathered. Thirdly, conclusions were derived and finally, recommendations were made based on the findings. Important papers selected mostly gave overviews on Africa and Nigeria and their construction processes, innovations in industrialization in Africa, issues regarding types of energy efficient strategies and building construction materials applicable in the construction industry in Africa, energy efficiency measures applicable to the Sub-Saharan African Space, Africa and the continent. Other areas of interest discussed include the building energy efficiency code, innovative energy efficiency building construction materials available in the construction industry that could be used in reducing major environmental damages of buildings on the environment in Nigeria and enforcing the building of environmentally friendly construction deliverables. Finally and of major importance is the highlights which the study gives on how policy interventions can either delay or accelerate the adoption of low carbon technologies such as renewable energy use. It also identifies reasons for noncompliance with modern technologies that enhance environmental sustainability by building construction stakeholders. This also translates towards achieving long term benefits of energy efficiency in Nigeria since the built environment professionals in Nigeria are guilty of designing huge buildings that contribute to emissions of harmful greenhouse gases and posing further threats of climate change.

3.0 DATA PRESENTATION

3.1 The Nigerian Construction Built Environment

It is a realizable fact to say shelter is the third most important need of man after the other basic necessities of food and clothing have been met. These are the factors that inform (Osuizugbo 2019) in affirming that buildings and human lives are complimentary roles in the sequence of man's ability to house themselves and their immediate households. Construction processes and activities in any built environment are measures to economic growth and development within the society and its immediate environment. In a study by (Abdullahi and Bala 2018), they observed that building activities enhance a countries economy and provides employment for the citizenry and infrastructural services. More so, they positively impact the socio economic well-being of the citizenry coupled with the huge housing deficit of seventeen million currently existing in Nigeria while also grappling with the huge infrastructural deficit that continues unabated. In conceptualizing and improving design of buildings in the Nigerian built environment, (Anumudu and Uchendu 2023) in their study argued that construction is both an art and science of infrastructural and structural development, while building construction is the process of allocating manpower and equipment to finishing construction projects that have been embarked upon. Building works do not only generate revenues and incomes thereby contributing in no small measure to a countries development, it also contributes immensely to other relevant sectors as the need arises (Okeke, Nnaemeka-Okeke and Awe 2023). The multiplier effects of the construction industry on the socio economic well-being of all other sectors of the economy and also enhancing the wealth of the nation cannot be overemphasized (Okoye 2016); thus creating all round advantages to small and medium scale construction industry players with a few multinational players in the sector, consisting mostly of private and public service clients that employs huge labor and manpower all year round, thereby oiling the wheels of the Nigerian economy positively. The construction industry in Nigeria is a process that primarily deals with project conceptualization, design and erection of the structures which consist mainly of residential, commercial, industrial and other allied buildings in the cityscape (Sholanke, Chen, Newo and Nwabefo 2019), these processes take time but eventually the buildings become habitable during their useful life and are demolished when they are no longer fit for the purpose for which they were originally

conceived. Therefore, the construction industry contributes its own quota to the revenues of both advanced and advancing nations in no small measure.

3.2 Processes and Methods of Building Projects in the Construction Space in Nigeria

Materials and building construction are the building blocks upon which every construction project is developed and domiciled within the built environment. In a study by (Ifeanyi and Adindu 2023), building materials are the backbone to the activities and products of construction projects worldwide. About 63% of building construction materials that find their way into the construction market are imported since the local manufacturers are not able to meet the enormous demand within the country. This is attributed to poor quality of production, lack of heavy demand on locally produced materials and low marketability of the construction products, which places a premium on imported construction materials. In investigating building transitions and developments with construction materials such as cement sandcrete, sustainable building units, (Edike, Ameh, Adenuga and Akintunde 2023) found that energy consumption of sustainable building units were lower than that of concrete blocks. This suggests that building materials used by developers and those involved in the building construction industry in Nigeria should base their selection on life cycle energy performance of the materials. As construction projects line up the horizon of the built environment in Nigeria, (Muhammed and Adindu 2023) emphasised the importance of construction materials which was said to have a monumental contribution to the creation in employment with associated increases in specialization of local artisans in the construction industry in Nigeria. In another study by (Muazu and Alibaba 2017), they argue that traditional building materials exist in abundance in the construction industry in Nigeria but they are dependent on the geographical location where they are domiciled. The authors advance that the local building materials are sustainable in local constitution and support the situation whereby the local materials are used in conjunction with conventional building materials over time. The traditional materials mentioned are: wood, stone, rammed earth, straw bales, clay bricks, sheep wool, hemp, fibers, cork, bamboo and coconut lumber which can be used for walls, floors and roof construction in buildings. In their research, (Stanley Ogbuagu and Okechukwu 2014) revealed that most building components used in erecting houses and offices in Nigeria come from China thereby increasing the construction costs of building projects and suggested that the Chinese government should invest in the local building materials market in Nigeria thereby reducing capital flight from the economy. Major construction materials in the country are cement, steel and tiles. Some researchers that investigated using these alternative building materials believe some of such alternative construction methods have manifested at a very minimal trajectory. In a research conducted in Ekiti State by (Alade, Oyebade and Nzewi 2018), the authors identified ten local building materials that could be complementary in achieving construction success in Nigeria. These include: stone, timber, laterite, clay and mud, bamboo, leaves and barks of trees, Palm Kernel Shells, wild coconut trees, animal wastes and dung.

3.3 Energy Efficiency Measures Adopted in Buildings in Nigeria and Developed Economies

Three design considerations towards achieving energy efficiency in buildings identified by (Oyalowo, Ohiro and Oginni 2018) include initial design considerations such as the building site, orientation, landscaping and the buildings layout form; building envelope systems including external wall finishes and thermal insulation; and building services like heating, air conditioning, ventilation and electrical systems. Other areas of energy efficiency and conservation in buildings, especially office structures, are associated with the building envelope system, the types of associated building services employed, maintenance and operations within the building and the behavior of the occupants within the buildings while also 'considering the changes in a building's microenvironment that improves energy efficiency within them. By Microenvironments, these researchers refer to green spaces within the building's immediate surrounding like plants and greenery, applications of sustainable roofs while also introducing water pools and water retaining bodies around the surrounding elements. In their study on achieving sustainability and energy efficiency in Nigerian households, (Mato, Labaran, Mukherjee, Saini and Faroug 2023) suggest that nine major reasons have influenced using energy efficiency in construction projects which are

identified as government supervision and government support. Other factors include economic and technical support, legal environment, building codes and enforcement, occupants behaviors, knowledge and information, awareness, equipment and technology including construction quality. In another study by (Alegbeleye, Nwaogu, Ifeoluwa, Adelerin and Damilola 2024) on evaluation of power consumption in buildings in the south of Nigeria, the authors suggest that effective ways of enhancing minimum consumption of power is achievable with having very effective building insulation system which are cost effective and affordable by the house owners. Another study on reductions in consumption levels of power usage and generation in buildings within the three major climatic areas in Nigeria, (Odunfa, Nnakwe and Odunfa 2018) suggest that energy efficiency within houses is achievable through the type of building orientation and the types of differences in materials compositions. In terms of building orientation, the researchers believe that the North/South longitudinal orientation achieved better energy efficiency. Further studies by (Okonta 2023) on impacts which materials of construction have on thermal comfort and cooling loads within buildings in Nigeria conclude that using sustainable materials and integrating other design strategies that enhance energy efficiency will be an advantage. Further suggestions of encouraging studies into sustainable designs peculiar to Nigeria could effectively play a vital role in achieving climate change mitigation techniques.

Similarly, (Ochedi and Taki 2023) on a framework approach on sustainable building design analysed using bioclimatic design approach by placing more emphasis on external coverings of buildings since this could provide lasting solutions to sustainability of buildings in Nigeria. In another study, (Ezema and Maha 2022) on achieving breakthroughs in reductions of consumption of energy in Multi-Storey business complexes within Lagos and its surroundings, identified five design strategies that enhance energy efficiency in these building types. These they identified as adoption of passive design strategies while also using remote controlled sensor equipment's that monitor thermal comfort within the buildings. They also suggest the use of energy efficiency lighting appliances, placing emphasis on reduction of energy waste and using renewable energy sources as power generating alternatives. Further studies by (Erebor, Ibem and Ezema 2021) on efficient control of consumption patterns in generation of power in complex multi-story commercial structures in Abuja, Nigeria identified twenty-nine of such applications which include building orientation, energy efficient landscape design and site selection. In another study by (Sholanke, Alugah, Ademo and Adisa 2021) on the effects of buildings energy consumption within complex structures highlighted the importance a buildings orientation plays in improving energy efficiency within the building.

In another study, (Djordjevic, Pekez, Novakovic, Bakator, Djurdjev, Cockalo and Jovanovic 2023), noted that using solar panels in urban neighborhoods are a good energy consumption reducing strategy at achieving lower rates in Serbia. Another major breakthrough in energy consumptions in buildings are the use of the newly developed organic biophase change integrated building envelopes. They have the ability to change their forms from liquid to solid and are further classified into organic and inorganic classes. Similarly, (Terhan and Ilgar 2023) also highlighted the importance of these building envelopes since they are able to transition from liquid to solid form at night and transform back to liquid form during the day, thereby maintaining comfortable thermal comfort properties within the buildings. Other breakthroughs in building energy efficiency according to (Sedighi, Qhazvini and Amidpour 2023) are the use of photo bioreactor building elements on the facades of buildings which are environmentally friendly materials. Microalgae interventions can also be employed; they are capable of sequestering the carbon dioxide released by buildings when implemented as energy efficient design strategies in buildings. Other mitigating strategies used in energy conservation in buildings are locally sourced fibres which are rich in locally sourced content. They contribute to achieving thermal insulation within buildings since they considerably do not harm the environment (Ulutaş, Balo and Topal 2023). Innovative technologies that are connected to building modelling systems can also be used as a way of ensuring energy efficiency in buildings. These innovative technologies range from smart metering systems and automated shading systems (Moghayedi, Hubner and `Michell 2022). All these systems have the capacity to increase the buildings energy performance in the long run when connected to a building modelling system that tracks a buildings energy performance.

In another study, (Aryal, Chaiwiwatworakul and Chirarattananon 2023) advance that by equipping the outdoor air units with power saving substitutes, effective cooling the radiant systems can effectively function while (Sadegig, Hejazymehr and Arefnia 2019) also studied office buildings in Tehran towards attaining energy efficiency and found that protecting the external walls with insulation materials such as glass fiber, quilt layer and application of louvres shading pattern with the angle of 10° , are suitable both in summer and winter as important strategies of reducing energy consumption patterns generally. Similarly, (Golzan, Pouyanmehr and Naeini 2023) also observed that in Tehran, the application of modular dynamic facades in office buildings at an angle of 30° , decrease energy consumptions within building spaces and recommended that investing in such building envelopes could usher in good returns on investments when applied to office buildings. There are a varied range of energy efficient building facades that are recommended for use in buildings, but the types and sizes to be used depend on climatic conditions and differences in performance abilities. Also, Yaman (2021) noted that wall panels that have green features, media and structural membranes could enhance future developments of energy efficient buildings.

Furthermore, (Wan, Ding, Runeson and Liu 2023) applied simulations in a large office building in China and confirmed that installing LED lighting systems as well as installing a frequency conversion device for the water chillers, contributed to reductions in energy consumptions within office spaces. The world currently is focusing on decarbonisation of the built environment and steps at achieving this are current issues being investigated by researchers. To achieve this within Tokyo Metropolitan Districts of Japan, (Shono, Yamaguchi, Perwez, Ma, Dai and Shimoda 2023) suggested the installation of renewables and their complementing technologies and introduction of photovoltaic panels on the facades externally. The system uses the energy generated by them to power the buildings and reduces adverse temperature rises that occur during the day. Applying thin layers of nanocomposite coatings as wall insulations in the form of coated polyurethane nanocomposites has thus become a common practice, thereby preventing heat loss and improving thermal comfort. Another major milestone at implementing efficient use of power within a building is the recent introduction of the principle of urban block morphology which is a highly efficient way of controlling energy consumptions based on researches conducted in China by (Xu, Lu, Zhang, Xie, Mendis and Du 2023). This is now the current discuss among researchers, as it was observed that energy used to cool indoor spaces in a building faces further reduction in alternating building arrangements within urbanized formations.

3.4 The Building Energy Efficiency Code in Nigeria

Sustainability, climate change issues, efficient utilization of energy and sustainable design are relatively new concepts, but construction professionals knowledge of these phenomena's are rapidly growing due to the high energy consumptions associated with buildings and infrastructural development. In the Nigerian building construction stage, there seems to be a lack of an effective code based system for guiding building energy efficiency. Investigations revealed that policy documents are the only tools used in compliance with standards and these are not implemented regularly due to lack of adequate monitoring and evaluation by enforcing agencies due to corruption. In advanced countries, the high premium placed on efficient use of power within structures is leading to the establishment of (LEED) of the United States which is their rating system, (ASHRAE) and Globe rating systems which were decided to be adopted by countries around the world during the world summit on climate change in Brazil in 1992 (Kawuwa, Sani, Mustapha and Ishaku 2015). In a research on developing an effective methods of enhancing building compliance with a code system for Nigeria, (Geisler, Österreicher and Macharm 2018) noted that following the review of other existing codes within the building construction space, preparing the building energy efficiency code started with one major preparatory activity which was developing a building code package for Nigeria. Major areas of concentration of the guidelines include fully exploiting climatic adaptation strategies while also limiting additional costs of using specific materials; and also considering educational intelligence of monitoring and compliance technical officers in the construction space. This the authors observed (Geissler *et al.* 2018), was the first Nigerian Building Energy Efficiency Guideline which was established by the Federal Ministry of Power, Works and Housing in June 2016 and

touches on energy efficiency of buildings and sub divides them into passive and active design strategies. The guideline stipulates design procedures on implementing these guidelines within buildings concluding with case studies of building energy efficiency in two building types, that is, residential and office buildings. The authors asserted that these guidelines which started in 2016 with other stakeholders in the building space commenced in the Federal Capital territory. It was made mandatory that the code is used for the ministry's buildings, and applied in all other projects in Nigeria. The energy efficiency minimum requirements at the initial stage, covered residential and office buildings. After series of simulations and modeling of a standard building that was used as a test case and other international references were reviewed, a common minimum standard for building energy efficiency was arrived at 40%. These were made mandatory leading to project commissioning. A direct advantage of this was during the development of the code, it was suggested that regular training should be carried out for the staff that are involved in building approvals at the building control agencies to maintain compliance and implementation. Also noteworthy is the fact that these guidelines are mandatory for new builds, commercial buildings and living apartments. The code stipulates that buildings that do not comply with the code fail approval and signing off with the Building code and guidelines.

3.5 Innovative Energy Efficient Building Materials and Components within Nigeria's Built Environment

Adopting energy efficient components of construction as alternative building materials for building projects in Nigeria has not gained widespread usage but there exists a few of the building components which when used will excel in reducing and resolving climate change challenges within the Nigerian built environment. To support this argument, (Kusimo, Olugu and Ismail 2023) in a study conducted in Lagos on the use of microencapsulated phase change materials on buildings, indicated, efficient energy consumption levels in the long run, when these materials were used. Similarly, (Kolajo and Omoniyi 2023) suggested that due to the huge urban migration in Nigeria, researches are ongoing to investigate using lignocellulosic resources which are forest wastes, agricultural wastes and also include industrial remnants used in the production of wood based panel boards for building envelope systems. This can be made possible by using walnut shells as additives to clay and fired at high temperatures. The combination of the two constituent materials was found to be effective in achieving sustainable energy efficient bricks. Similarly, researches in Southern Africa by (Aneke and Shabangu 2021) where scrap waste plastic and foundry sand were mixed in different proportions to act as building envelope systems. These were developed in an attempt to provide solutions that are resource efficient through product life extension. An advantage of this sustainable combination is the production of green efficient bricks that can be used for load bearing walls, towards providing sustainable housing in South Africa and developing countries. In a bid to discover innovative energy efficient green construction materials in the construction industry, (Kuuribo, Shokry, Hassanein, Asawa and Mahmoud 2023) explored using alternatives of reused glasses, wood and other wastes like paneling materials for efficiency in construction projects. These authors believe that the innovation could be used as an alternative building material different from the current conventional materials being implemented that have a higher potential in future projects, due mainly to their cost effectiveness. To produce low-cost housing in the Indonesian construction industry, (Zuraida, Dewancker and Margono 2023) suggested the use of disposable diaper substituted for fine aggregates. The authors are certain that the composite material will compare favorably with existing conventional building materials, particularly when they are employed in the construction of low cost housing.

Alternative building materials components have become an important issue that needs immediate attention due to the current issues of global warming. In fulfilling this all important mandate of improving reductions in greenhouse gases emissions in buildings, (Soni, Das, Yusuf, Kamyab and Chelliapan 2022) advance the use of other innovative measures like a combination using composites of waste plastics for tiling. Also, adding sustainable glass fiber into sustainable concrete produced with silica fume and additions of coconut shell has been suggested for use in the built environment, because in the long run, they help to accomplish a level of sustainable concrete with durable strength and stability. Quite interestingly, there are further ongoing studies on using agricultural wastes as components of buildings

that could act as binding materials comparable to cementitious slurry, coarse and aggregates. Other researchers (Sathiparan, Anburuvel and Selvam 2023) are of the opinion that these are other forms of energy efficient building materials in construction deliverables. According to the authors, such agricultural wastes are groundnut shell ashes which are presently disposed of as waste. In using this substitute agricultural waste, the advantages derived from it are construction cost savings and environmental sustainability. The major factors responsible for the global challenge towards getting alternatives to cement as a building material is due to the fact that cement is a major pollutant to the environment. In addition, (Martinez-Garcia, Jagadesh, Zaid, Serbanoiu, Fraile-Fernandez, Prado-Gil, Qaidi and Grădinaru 2022) agree that this has necessitated the possibility of using waste wood ash which offers double advantages in being environmentally friendly. Construction is currently faced with a lot of interconnected challenges stemming from the fact that there is a huge need for housing due to the urban population pull. Therefore, (Maraveas 2020) advocate for a look inward towards using natural agro waste resources for the production of construction materials. These products were confirmed to be effective because they adhered to established building standards. In realization of finding further alternative construction materials for other component areas of building construction projects, (Salahudeen, Kpardong and Francis 2023) suggest using geopolymers towards the production of pavements, thereby improving the efficiency for flexible clay pavements. Furthermore, (Latha, Murugesan and Thomas 2023) have also explored using waste derivable from biodegradable materials as an alternative to cementitious materials for building components making the built environment carbon free and sustainable. While in another study, (Delcasse, Rahul, Abhilash and Pavan 2017) have also suggested the development of papercrete concrete which is a new composite material comprising of waste papers and cement which can be used for non-load bearing walls only. Additionally, materials like coconut fibers and fly ash can be added to improve their compressive strengths and further additions of color pigments can improve their aesthetic and design versatility. The use of groundnut shells which are being transformed to new products of building construction is also been developed which can be applied to substitute the need for cementitious materials used as binders. In a related study by (Abd-Elrahman, Agwa, Mostafa and Youssf 2023), they believe composite materials are effective in achieving ultra-high strength concrete for building construction projects. In an effort at further research on sustainable building materials, (Mohlala, Bodunrin, Awosusi, Daramola, Cele and Olubambi 2016) suggest that efforts should be intensified towards using the large generated agricultural residues in Nigeria and South Africa namely, corncobs and sugarcane, in building materials development which the authors believe can also not be ignored. Though there is a lack of awareness in using bamboo for reinforcement in the Kenyan construction industry, (Habibi, Obonyo and Memari 2023) noted that the use of bamboo is gaining prominence towards its application in low cost housing due to its environmentally friendly nature. Similarly in study conducted by (Eze, Ugulu, Onyeagam and Adegboyega 2021), it was observed that the most commonly used sustainable materials in the South Eastern parts of Nigeria are straw and other environmentally friendly materials. Other authors (Olofinnade, Anwulidiunor, Ogundipe and Ajimalofin 2023) suggest reusing agricultural or marine-based waste in achieving a carbon free built environment. In addition, (Kareem, Adedayo, Adeosun, Akinwusi, Orogbade, Ayanlere and Bello 2023) suggest that there is an advantage gained by incorporating cashew leaf ash as an environmental friendly building component.

3.6 Green Building Concepts in Building Construction Projects in Nigeria

Towards advancing and encouraging using energy efficient building components in the construction industry in Nigeria, (Adedeji 2018) affirmed that there has been an extensive innovative usage of building components in the country's capital city. These materials are considered as good alternatives to sandcrete blocks which are currently very expensive to purchase. In Ethiopia, (Gelan 2022) investigated the use of sustainable components and technologies in the development of construction works placing emphasis on a bank building project. The major observations made were that using green components saved a lot of energy. Similarly, studies on commercial properties in Lagos by (Ola and Adjekophori 2018) revealed that the green features mostly used in commercial building construction project in Lagos are careful orientation, low energy lighting design, use of renewable energy, use of maximum daylighting and the use

of energy efficient and eco-friendly equipment's. In a green building housing project in Lusaka Zambia, (Sichali and Banda 2017) used the American LEED rating system to assess the buildings and rated them high. Successes recorded were based on the applications of sustainable design and sustainability. The concepts include: sustainable site planning, safeguarding water and water efficiency, energy efficiency, renewable energy conservation and reuse of materials and resources. From studies analysed using green building technologies and features, it was observed that the use of the green construction systems in sub-Saharan Africa is low. Therefore, there is a need for awareness campaigns about the green building concept amongst construction industry professionals and stakeholders. However, in South Africa, the use of green building concepts were introduced to curb the negative effects of construction activities. Similarly, (Oguntona, Akinradewo, Ramorwalo, Aigbavboa and Thwala 2019) identified key deliverables achieved by the use of green building concepts in the country to include: improved indoor air quality, ecosystem protection, increased energy efficiency, enhancement of health and wellbeing of building occupants and minimized carbon dioxide emissions. Likewise, to determine the level of green building adoption and implementation in the Ghanaian construction industry, (Anzagira, Duah, Badu, Simpeh, Abanyie and Marful 2022) found that the five most applied of the green technologies include optimizing site planning, building orientation and configuration, natural ventilation, natural lighting, application of energy efficient lighting and permeable paving systems.

3.7 Appraisal of Green Building Construction in Nigeria

There are multiple benefits to be experienced and achieved in the construction of energy efficient, sustainable and green buildings in the built environment. In a study (Umesi, Mohammed and Yunusa 2023), residential green building construction techniques and the use of sustainable practices in the development of buildings in Nigeria, are yet to be fully utilized, while in the international community, these systems of construction have been fully embraced. Critical factors that enhance the development of green building construction are the coordination of designers and contractors technical and innovation skills within the market. Others are governments co-funding, availability of incentives and collaboration with research institutes for the manufacture and production of green building components and materials. It has been observed by (Kanda, Lusweti, Ngugi, Irungu, Omondi and Waweru 2023) that there exists health and wellness benefits associated with green buildings which has encouraged its adoption in Kenyan municipalities. The authors found in their study that most of the respondents are aware of the principal concepts that make up green building adoption and encourages their wider promotion. The concepts include: water efficiency, energy efficiency, sustainable materials, sustainable site practices and indoor environmental quality. While listing and identifying the importance of green practices, (Nduka and Ogunsanmi 2015) highlighted the green building design practices adopted by construction professionals as: site sustainability, material and resource conservation, energy conservation, building and maintenance operations, health and safety of occupants, conservation of water and recycling and waste reduction. Also, it has been suggested that the major reasons for adopting green building materials were emission's minimization, low running costs and reusability, low thermal and energy consumption efficiency, low cost and high health and safety considerations and waste minimization. These, the authors emphasized will further reduce the impacts of buildings on the built environment thereby making the country play their own fundamental role in reducing the emissions of greenhouse gases into the environment

3.8 Barriers to the use of Sustainable Construction Methods in the Nigerian Building Construction Industry

Due to the urgent demand of mitigating the effects of buildings on the environment with its inherent challenges of addressing the global climate change albatross, building construction professionals both in developed and developing economies have continued to find ways and means of addressing this. In acknowledging that greenhouse gases emissions from construction industry activities have contributed to the rise in natural disasters, (Daniel, Oshineye and Itodo 2018) highlight that these natural disasters are similar to those being experienced around most coastal cities around the world. In addition, (Melgar and Marquez 2022) agree that the AEC industry must prioritize the use of new technologies and methods that

would make buildings more energy efficient and sustainable if the world wants to further achieve reductions in greenhouse gases emissions into the environment. Sustainable construction is concerned with planning and designing of building construction sites, comfortable indoor environmental air quality, energy and materials usage and the use of water within the buildings (Osuizugbo, Oyeyipo, Lahanmi, Morakinyo and Olaniyi 2020).

Table 1: Key barriers to sustainable construction methods in Nigeria

S/N	BARRIER CATEGORIES	BARRIERS
1.	Government and Regulatory	Lack of government support Lack of relevant laws and regulations
2.	Knowledge and Awareness	Lack of public knowledge Inadequate level of awareness
3.	Economic	Poverty High cost of sustainable materials
4.	Cultural and Social	Social and Cultural barriers Clients' indifference in buildings

The authors identified a lack of government support for the adoption of sustainable construction methods, a lack of relevant laws and regulations to streamline the use of such construction methods, building clients indifference to the use of sustainable construction in their projects, low levels of awareness and the fear of the perceived cost of sustainable building materials. The current push for sustainable construction has several advantages with the reductions of carbon footprints as the most fundamental. In Nigeria, there is a lack of awareness of the uses and advantages of sustainable materials due to lack of public knowledge and demand for the use of sustainable building materials (Madueme and Nnaji 2023). In their study, (Adindu, Musa, Nwajugu, Yusuf and Yisa 2020) found that there is a paucity of literature on the uses of sustainable construction methods in the construction industry in Nigeria despite the enormous advantages that are associated with their use. According to the authors, the advantages are in the form of cost reductions, waste minimization during construction, enormous health benefits associated with them, health and productivity gains and the reductions in the irrational consumption of natural resources from the built environment. They further noted that the reason why the Nigerian built environment professionals have not embraced sustainable construction is as a result of the lack of availability of sustainable construction materials, lack of experience in areas of sustainable design, poverty and a lack of low urban investment as key barriers to the adoption of sustainable design processes in the Nigerian building construction industry.

One of the other innovative ways of enhancing the survival of the built environment is a new concept known as green building design which (Dalibi, Feng, Shuangqin, Sadiq, Bello and Danja 2017) agree is based on the foundation of sustainable construction. The authors argue that, buildings that are resource efficient are those sensitive to the environment, environmentally friendly and have positive impacts on the occupants within the buildings. While they believe that there are advantages to be derived from the application of this form of construction method, they have identified several barriers and challenges inhibiting the adoption of this method. They identified lack of green building technical know-how by the professionals in the Nigerian Construction industry, lack of cost and performance related data about green building design, perceived high cost of green building construction, as some of the hindrances. Others are the perceived associated risks of green building construction, social, cultural and technological barriers, non-availability of green building materials and the high cost of imported ones and a lack of data for using green building assessment. This (Toriola-Coker, Alaka, Bello, Ajayi, Adeniyi and Olopade 2021) attributed as part of the identified barriers to the use of sustainable construction methods in the Nigerian building construction industry. Others they believe are the poor sustainability academic curriculum of education being taught students of courses related to building and construction in the Nigerian institutions

of higher learning. The authors advocate for the need for construction professionals to fully embrace sustainability as a design concept. There is also the lack of a widely operational National Building Code that addresses issues pertinent to sustainable construction in the country which (Omopariola, Albert and Windapo 2019) identify as a major mitigating barrier.

The key themes and patterns identified are:

- a) Lack of awareness and knowledge: Both professionals and the public lack understanding of sustainable construction methods and their benefits.
- b) Regulatory gaps: There's a shortage of government support, relevant laws, and a comprehensive building code addressing sustainability.
- c) Economic challenges: The perceived high costs and lack of investment are significant deterrents.
- d) Technical limitations: There's a lack of expertise, materials, and data related to sustainable construction.
- e) Educational shortcomings: Current academic curricula don't adequately cover sustainability in construction

4.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The realities of climate change are real and the need to reduce the trends of global warming by reducing dependence on fossilized based products in electricity generation has become the primary concern of most construction stakeholders. In appraising the use of energy efficient measures in the development of the built environment in Nigeria, it is important to note that this provides great opportunities' in enhancing energy efficiency while also improving the current energy generation and consumption patterns nationwide. The research highlights the critical advantages energy efficiency plays within Nigeria. Therefore by adopting energy efficient measures, these have huge advantages to benefit from, especially in the industrial and commercial sectors which consume the highest energy for air conditioning and thermal control regulation within such buildings. Several benefits abound in adopting these strategies while developing structures within the built environment. Firstly, it is believed by applying these strategies like using energy efficient lighting, smart grids, regular energy audits and optimization of industrial processes, these could greatly reduce energy wastages. This concept upholds the sustainable communities' development and ensuring habitable and livable urban environments. The implications of these findings are multidimensional and they include firstly, acting as a guide to policy makers and building designers on the energy efficiency measures to be adopted which will enhance the building users wellness. Secondly, it is also agreed that further steps by policymakers would be creating additional incentives for construction of energy efficient buildings that improves sustainability in Nigeria while also achieving the SDGs. However, a lack of awareness and advantages of using sustainable components was found to be responsible for the slow take off observed locally. Construction stakeholders are aware of energy efficient measures obtainable generally, their adoption rate is low. Some of the reasons for this is the lack of enforcement by the regulating bodies and inadequate policy frameworks. Further mitigating factors are a lack of standardized in-house green building rating systems that acts as a check for compliance.

In Nigeria, the government is faced with an enormous housing challenge to the tune of 17 million and providing solutions to this housing gap should include attempts at achieving sustainability. Therefore, with the increase in the impact of buildings on the environment, it has become imperative to consider controlled measures at mitigating their effects on the environment. It is believed that the adaptation of energy and environmental policies, particularly suited for the Nigerian built environment would act as checks and balances in adoption and enforcement of energy efficiency and sustainable design. Suggestions for effective collaboration amongst professionals should form bodies where they can all work together in protecting the environment, both locally and on the global level. Another key factor in adopting these innovative methods is ensuring the wellness of building occupants within the spaces they live in due to the embodied energy of the materials of construction, thereby enhancing the selection of appropriate design features that promotes wellness in buildings. A case of mitigating against sick building syndrome is key to ensuring wellness. Tax incentives could be a working contribution where the costs of

energy efficient and sustainable building materials can be made available at cheaper rates to encourage the local construction manufacturers and importers in meeting the desired goals of supply and demand. This is important because of the huge employment generation that would be created when the adoption of these innovative construction systems become available in the market. Again, there is an important advantage derivable from adoption of energy efficiency and sustainable design practices which include huge financial savings derived from these kinds of practices, both to the construction professionals and the clients that initiates building and infrastructural project. Also, educational institutions of higher learning are tasked with the responsibility of assisting in teaching students construction processes that apply energy efficiency and sustainable design practices, as well as organizing conferences and workshops for professionals to further create awareness. One of the studies limitations is that it relied on literature from only six repositories of peer reviewed articles downloaded from these data bases. It excluded data from grey literature and technical papers. This study is further limited in ascertaining the rate of adoption of energy efficient materials compared to needed levels of compliance in office buildings, commercial buildings, industrial buildings and residential housings. This forms one of the viable areas for further research. In the long run, it is intended that inferences derived from the review would be beneficial to construction stakeholders, government policy makers, academia, building materials supplies and the business communities towards enhancing the development of the built environment further in Nigeria.

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